

A REPORT ON TWO FIBER-OPTIC-TETHERED UNDERWATER VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the performance of two fiber-optic-tethered, remote-controlled, underwater vehicle systems recently developed at the Naval Ocean Systems Center (NOSC) Hawaii Laboratory. The Fiber Optic Cable Underwater Stereo (FOCUS) vehicle, completed in September 1978, is believed to be one of the first of its kind. The Miniature Optical Stereo Evaluation System (MOSES) is summarized here, but its telemetry is reported in greater detail elsewhere in these Proceedings. Features of both vehicle systems include bidirectional transmission over a single optical fiber, stereo television viewing, and onboard energy storage for propulsion. Last year, a miniature sonar and computer-aided voice control were demonstrated with the FOCUS analog telemetry. MOSES incorporates digital telemetry and extends the length of the optical tether from 2.5 kilometers (FOCUS) to 8 kilometers.

INTRODUCTION

For many years, the advantages and disadvantages of Remotely Controlled Vehicles (RCV's) have been known to those who work in the undersea environment. This interest has been intensified recently by the petroleum industry, which has expanded research and development in unmanned inspection and repair of submarine pipelines. (1,2) The need to extend both the task- and depth capabilities of present and future RCV's has become apparent to both the commercial and military undersea communities.

Realizing the operational advantages that RCV's could gain from fiber optic tether cables, the NOSC Hawaii Laboratory initiated development of an experimental, fiber-optic-tethered vehicle (FOCUS) in 1977. Its successful operation has shown the very large impact that fiber optics will have on future remotely-tethered systems, due to the simultaneous increase in telemetry bandwidth and reduction in tether cable diameter.

Recent advances in longer-wavelength, lower-attenuation, lower-dispersion, fiber optics technology have been applied in a second demonstration undersea vehicle. The Miniature Optical

Stereo Evaluation System (MOSES) is being assembled under a NOSC-funded Internal Exploratory Development (IED) program. MOSES will demonstrate the ability to transmit digital, high bandwidth data from depths of 6 kilometers (20,000 feet).

Both of these telemetry links operate in a full duplex mode. That is, both use wavelength division multiplexing to allow simultaneous telemetry in both directions through a single optical fiber.

FOCUS

FOCUS was built to demonstrate (and gain operational experience with) the monitoring and control of a small undersea RCV through a tether cable which contained a single optical fiber. This demonstration was to utilize the wide bandwidth characteristic of fiber optic telemetry in an undersea vehicle communications link. (Such bandwidth allows the use of two high-resolution (400-line) TV cameras, as well as an instrumentation channel which supports a variety of sensors.) The original design goals for FOCUS included:

1. An electro-optic command/control cable.
2. A platform for high-resolution stereo TV.
3. 30-meter operating depth.
4. 1.5-knot speed (0.77 m/sec).
5. Battery power, with a 2-hour operating time.
6. A highly maneuverable inspection and survey system incorporating three reversible, variable speed thrusters (one for vertical control and two axially mounted for horizontal propulsion and control).
7. Relatively simple, low cost design incorporating off-the-shelf hardware and proven technology.

In its final configuration, FOCUS met or exceeded all of these goals. The resulting pseudo-free-swimming vehicle (figure 1) is 2 meters in length, 0.75 meters high and, while slightly buoyant in water, weighs 550 kilograms in air.

The initial FOCUS design concept included a full duplex optical data link, but technology in 1977 was not yet ready to support this feature. Because the laboratory was simultaneously involved in the development of such a duplexer, it was decided to use a single optical fiber in the tether cable.

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Figure 1. FOCUS Vehicle In Test Pool With The F/O Tether Trailing To The Right

This fiber was initially used only for high frequency uplink data, and was graded index with an attenuation of 6 dB/km at 0.83 μm . The (buffered) fiber was served with a helix of 15 copper-clad-steel wires which, when used in conjunction with a seawater return, provided the low frequency (down-link) control channel. The tether cable ⁽³⁾ (figure 2) is 2.5 mm in diameters. It has a 55-kg breaking strength (at 0.8% strain), and a 1.27-cm minimum bending radius.

The fiber optic link supports the transmission of two 400-line TV signals (stereo pair), plus an instrumentation channel onto which is multiplexed heading, depth and other system monitors. These three channels are frequency division multiplexed (FDM) within the 100-kHz to 38-MHz band, and are used to modulate the intensity of a 0.85- μm laser diode. This fiber optic channel operates at a small fraction of its maximum bandwidth capacity. The downlink (electrical) data channel uses digital pulse code modulation (PCM) at 2 Kb/s, and transmits all necessary vehicle control signals.

The FOCUS communications link was originally demonstrated over 700 meters of tether. To lessen topside cable handling problems during tests and demonstrations, the tether has since been shortened to 175 meters. Maximum uplink length is about 2500 meters in this analog mode; a limitation set by the high signal/noise ratio required for such telemetry.

Early in 1979, a full-duplex, bidirectional optical fiber communication link was installed in the FOCUS vehicle.^(3,4,5) The uplink remained as it was, but downlink control data are now transmitted optically to the vehicle at 1.06 μm . Since the copper-clad-steel conductors are no longer required (electrically), the cable could be replaced with a much smaller tether.

Power for the three thrusters and the onboard electronics is provided by eight lead acid batteries, housed in four battery pods suspended from the bottom of the vehicle. Propulsion is provided by three modified variable speed thrusters obtained from Farallon MKIII diver propulsion vehicles. The maximum speed of the vehicle is about 1.5 knots (0.77 meter/sec).

Continuously-variable turning rates and reversible thrusters enable the vehicle to rotate about its vertical axis. This control and thruster configuration results in a highly maneuverable, easily controlled system.

The control console contains all topside electronics, including the stereo viewing display. The stereo display uses orthogonally-oriented TV monitors and a beam splitting mirror. The images combined by the mirror have been polarized to allow stereo viewing using a properly polarized set of glasses. This method of stereo display is also used on MOSES.

Most undersea RCV's that have been proposed or are presently being built require manual vehicle control, while requiring the operator to control or attend to other tasks---e.g., navigation and

Figure 2. FOCUS Cable Cross Section

operation of tools. One must always be concerned about the danger that such simultaneous (and quite different) tasks will overload the operator. If voice could be used to control vehicle movement, then the operator would have greater freedom to concentrate his efforts on more demanding tasks.

With the support of another NOSC IED program, computer-aided voice control was incorporated in the FOCUS control system in 1979 as a feasibility demonstration.⁽⁶⁾ (See figure 3.) While extensive operator testing was not completed, subjective responses from numerous operators indicated that the vehicle was easy to control, and that little time was required for them to become proficient in its use.

Figure 3. FOCUS Control Console With Computer-Aided Voice Control

MOSES

The maximum tether length possible for FOCUS was estimated to be 2.5 kilometers---a limit set by its use of analog telemetry at high frequencies and at the high attenuation wavelength of 0.83 μm . This limit would not allow the system to be operated at great depths. Since 90% of the ocean floor is shallower than 6 kilometers, a design tether length of 8 kilometers was chosen for MOSES.

The MOSES uplink (data) telemetry operates at a wavelength of 1.25 μm . At this wavelength, the tether cable could, in theory, be as long as 70 kilometers; subject to the further constraint that the bandwidth-length product $BL \leq 10 \text{ GHz/km}$. The major MOSES design goals were:

1. Optical telemetry through a 1.27-mm-diameter, 8-km cable.
2. Full duplex data transmission over a single optical fiber in this cable, using wavelength division multiplexing.
3. Provide a stable platform for two high-resolution, monochrome television cameras configured in a stereo pair.
4. 200-meter demonstration depth.

5. Battery powered, two-hour mission.
6. Maneuvering for X-Y translation plus rotation.

The MOSES optical telemetry system incorporates digital modulation techniques to allow long transmission distances.⁽⁷⁾ It is a full duplex system, and operates at wavelengths of 0.83 μm (command) and 1.25 μm (data). Command/control data for vehicular functions are transmitted at a 2 Kb/s rate. High frequency instrumentation signals (two monochrome television channels plus low frequency vehicle status data) are multiplexed onto a 120 Mb/s serial data stream for uplink transmission. The optical duplexers have insertion losses less than 2 dB, with cross-channel separation greater than 50 dB.^(3,8)

The 1.25- to 1.3- μm band was chosen for the uplink because of minimal material dispersion. The dispersion has been measured to be less than 1 ns over an 8-km cable when a single-mode injection laser is used. In the future, the optimum operating wavelengths for duplex operation probably will be 1.3 μm and 1.55 μm ; to take advantage of minimum optical dispersion at 1.3 μm and minimum optical attenuation at 1.55 μm .

The opto-mechanical tether cable (figure 4) was designed specifically to meet the requirements of the MOSES system. It employs a graded index optical fiber (ITT-EOPD, Roanoke, VA) buffered with RTV-184 and HYTREL-7246 to a diameter of 0.5 mm. (The entire fiber was subjected to a 1.0% proof strain.) The loadbearing structure is a 0.25-mm-thick annulus of KEVLAR-49 in a void-filling epoxy matrix. The overall diameter of the (polypropylene jacketed) cable is 1.27 mm. The loadbearing structure was applied at Air Logistics Corp. (Pasadena, CA), and final jacketing was done at South Bay Cable Co. (Idyllwild, CA). These processes did not increase the fiber's optical attenuation. The cable characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. MOSES CABLE CHARACTERISTICS

Cable Length	8.2 km
Fiber Core Diameter	55 μm
Fiber O.D.	125 μm
Optical Attenuation	5.0 dB/km @ 0.85 μm 2.78 dB/km @ 1.06 μm 3.7 dB/km @ 1.25 μm
Overall Cable Diameter	1.27 mm
Ultimate Strength	103 Kg (226 lbs) at 2.1% strain
Specific Gravity	1.166
Weight	1.48 Kg/km (0.993 lb/1000')

The tether cable does show high attenuation at 1.25 μm ; higher than would be expected for premium grade fibers manufactured today. (It was the best strong fiber of this length available in the U.S. at the time of its purchase in 1978.) Even with this higher attenuation, the cable easily supports the 120 Mb/s uplink channel over an 8.2-km length.

The vehicle configuration is shown in figure 5. In its normal operating mode, the vehicle hangs

Figure 4. MOSES Optical Cable

suspended from its tether. Two horizontal thrusters provide X-Y translation and rotational maneuverability. Power for the thrusters, lights and electronics is provided by pressure-compensated lead acid batteries. The 96-cm x 60-cm x 53-cm vehicle weighs approximately 34 kilograms in air, and has an in-water weight of 2.5 kilograms.

SUMMARY

The FOCUS and MOSES systems demonstrate that fiber optic technology is mature, and that it is ready for generalized application to tethered submersibles. Subsystems which clearly will benefit from the use of fiber optics include cable handling, data transmission, power transmission (via separation), viewing and navigation.

Furthermore, these demonstrations show that full application of fiber optics in the design of tethered submersibles will allow many new approaches to (and sophistication for) such systems. MOSES, with its digital telemetry system and stereo TV, is an example of one such approach.

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Figure 5. MOSES Vehicle Configuration

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Technical notes are working documents and do not represent an official policy statement of NOSC.